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A REVIEW OF 5G TECHNOLOGY USE IN SELF DRIVING CARS

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ABSTRACT

Following the 4G standard is the upcoming standard which was told to be implemented by the end of 2020 is the growth and implementation of 5G also known as the 5th generation. The technology offers so much advantages and can be helpful in various applications. One of them can be the use of this technology in self-driving cars, which is the part of Intelligent transport system(ITS). The self-driving cars is the area which is looked upon closely in the recent times, this development makes human intervention very less or no human inputs are required except the destination where he wants to travel to. The rest can be done by these self-driving cars as to collect which is the best route for travel and driving the cars based on the surrounding environmental conditions. In this paper we have discussed the challenges, advantages disadvantages and in future what can be the trends and its scope of development.

KEYWORDS:

5G, self-driving cars, vehicular communication

INTRODUCTION

With advancement in technology there is a huge reliance on the wireless industry which aims to foster the Next-Gen technology. 5G is taking hold over the technology and will expand the network to facilitate a vast diversity of devices and services connection between industries with improved performance and offers high data rate (up to 20 Gbps).

In the modern communication era the vehicle is being a very important part and plays a crucial role in the future development of science. Modern communication era that provides high connectivity, high reliability and low latency transmission. The safety information is what the Vehicular applications highly rely upon. This information must be send out from each vehicle so that the other vehicles can get to know about the others, this might lead to a lot of traffic in the network but with high throughput this can be achieved with good efficiency.

Wireless Access for Vehicular Environments program (WAVE) has part of IEEE 802.11p, which is used for vehicular communication. WAVE is occupying the 5.9GHz frequency band which is unlicensed band of frequency. Dedicated Short-Range Communications (DSRC) is supported by the IEEE 802.11p standard, and the support is also extended to European Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) initiative by developing ITS-G5 standard. V2X aims to facilitate highly reliable and efficient communication without reliance on GSM. Sensors used in V2X communication are very sophisticated and uses the sensors which can cover more than the line of sight or far vision sensors, also called as. Warning during the collisions and speed limiters or speed filters, electronic parking sensors and electronic toll collection are also the high technology sensors used for V2V and V2I.

Technology provides evidences of great capabilities to help and foster future generation transportation system.V2X communication has unique characteristics to enable intelligent transport system. There are many encryption models that have been used but there is no secured security model that is secure enough. There are some concerns in widespread deployment of V2X but advancement in technology and anticipated benefits can make it happen

LITREATURE REVIEW

A. 5G technology

With the development of mobile networks, the new technology which is started in some countries and which is going to be started in some countries is the 5G technology. These technology provides very high bandwidth and incredibly less latency. The features of this technology can be used in the advancement of vehicular communication. This new radio technology can be used for particular devices by providing very good accessibility and larger number of ties between the network members along with good area coverage factor.

B. Vehicular communication

With the development of automated vehicles, the collisions and traffic jams can be reduced to a very good extent. Safety and reliability of these vehicles is the top priority for any of the developers in this field. As shown in Fig(1) there are many types of vehicular communication where some of the are being used where some of them are in the development stage.

With the help of new technology like 5G which provide a greater speed of data processing and a very good reliability, there is a lot of scope to use this in the future.

Fig (1) – Types of vehicular communication

C. Self-driving cars

Robotic cars, automatic cars or self-driving cars are those cars which doesn't need any driver to control them. The sensor provides the required data for processing. Based on the external environment conditions and situations these have the intelligence to decide what action to be taken next and drive themselves. From the user perspective the first thing is the safety and reliability these cars provide and can these cars react faster according to the environment is the question in future.

CHALLENGES TO IMPLEMENT 5G IN DRIVERLESS CARS

The primary challenge would be to having the 5G network availability in widespread region. After the full development of this availability, the features can be then utilized in the further applications such as in intelligent transport systems. In continuation with this there can be chances where the cars may go out of coverage, like our mobiles sometimes doesn't have the signal. For instance, when the car is in basement parked, there should be a good coverage even there so as to work in all corner conditions.

From the ethical considerations point of view, in case there is an accident that takes place and by considering a corner case of death of an individual, who is responsible for the death, is it the manufacturer of the car or the

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one who provides network at that place. Adding on to this, the number of handovers from one network to the other will be immense and the base stations should have the capacity to withstand these handovers and the probability of those handovers should be very high and for the cent percent safety sake these probabilities must be unity. There is no assurance of these from the network providers.

The existing technology has a pre-defined physical layer of LTE V2X, so there is a challenge of developing the new physical layer we need to ensure that it is reliable to the other technologies as well.

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF 5G IN SELF DRIVING CARS

5G provides the development of new applications those can be useful for upcoming of the autonomous cars. With the use of 5G technology the inter communications is possible, these communications can be any type of vehicular communications. The network slicing is the major advantages the 5G technology provides which can be used by robotic cars. If the virtual network created is a dedicated network to the automated driving, there will be no traffic congestions and if happened so can be given a prior information to other services which is used in conjugation with this.

Low latency, bandwidth and data processing are the main first level advantages that is offered by the new radio network. As most of the sensor collects the data in a self-driving cars, these data needs to be processed as fast as possible and this is followed by the decisions the vehicle has to make based on the artificial intelligence and ML algorithms. The mobile technology offered will come in very handy in cases where the communication is between the infrastructure or other vehicles. Based on these data there can reduction or increase of the speed with which the cars may travel. Lastly the safety relevant objectives met by 5G are far better than those we have right now.

On the other hand, if we look closer on the lows of the 5G use in self-driving cars, the first thing is the security concern of the navigation systems. GPS and Global Navigation Satellite systems(GNSS) are very easily hackable and these systems can be eavesdropped from other external systems as well. Once this is done then the total control of these cars will be lost. Due to the over flooding of the data there can be sudden jam of the signal and in crucial situations the decisions can't be taken in a favourable manner.5G tries to combine the concept of IoT in the vehicles, but these has a major disadvantage of easy hacking. Having all these features of full security, low latency, high reliability and safety doesn't come at a cheaper price. The maintenance is not easy and cost of maintenance would also be high.

FUTURE SCOPE

The key feature of 5G for the automotive market is the C-V2X communications which enables the communication between different objects which has the ability of smart feature of communication with the other cars. This communication has very high throughput so that it can transfer the messages at very fast speed almost twice the older DSRC protocol. This speed is achieved with the help of the new methods of error correction and with new technology of compressors and decompressors.

Cloud based service, infrastructure communication will all enable the cars to communicate through majority of the objects it passes by so as to send and receive the data. This data can be while moving or while in a stationary position. This communication should enable vehicles with new capabilities and more economical to operate. Making such communication possible, will mean solving a series of design challenges in a rapidly evolving regulatory environment and complex engineering context.

The nonlinear exponential growth of the automobile industry has led to a lot of research in this field of science and this trend is expected to continue further in the upcoming years. 5G in vehicular communication will have a huge impact on the development of self-driving cars making them more reliable, ability to travel with greater speeds, and more importantly very safe to travel in.

With the help of huge amount of sensor data self-driving cars are becoming faster and acquiring more artificial intelligence. The amount of sensor data is no less than any other IoT devices adoption would. The driver can be full hands-free along the journey of the car which is main autopilot feature. An added benefit is the availability of the information and entertainment feature that is enabled by the 5G will be available for the passengers in

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self-driving cars. This feature will bind the service provider along with the driverless cars to enable very good communication in and out of the car. This bond between them will help for the further data analysis and security

CONCLUSION

In this paper we have discussed the use of the new technology that can be adopted in vehicular communication. This new technology has its ups and downs but depending on the application where its being used. In countries like India where the traffic conditions are very different each day, the vehicle should have the ability to adopt to all corner conditions. There is a lot of research that needs to be done on 5G technology uses in self-driving cars to become a reality. The infrasture development is also the major concern as of today. More and more companies are looking forward to these developments and working on the research and development side of it. Finally, can all these be done with the affordable price, so that common people can be helped by these services.

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